

Prediction of potential biomarkers for Glioblastoma

Authors

Akshay Vemulapalli, SkoolMentor, <powerakshay@outlook.com>

Juan Caballero Pérez*, SkoolMentor, <juan.caballero.perez@gmail.com>

* Corresponding author

Abstract

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most aggressive cancer that occurs in the brain, and it the most common brain primary tumour. Currently, there is no known way to prevent this type of cancer. Biomarkers, could be indicators of cancer progression inside the body in a non-invasive way, they are critical to the development of medical treatments for cancer, but there are not many that can be used for cancer and fewer for GBM.

The main objective of this project was to identify candidate biomarkers that can assist in glioblastoma diagnosis and treatment development. First, we used public sources such as the GDC repository to collect gene expression data from tumor samples. Then, we looked to identify differentially expressed genes, performed functional analysis, and annotated these genes. With these findings, we performed survival analysis to evaluate which genes could had a significant effect on the survival of the GBM patients. Finally, we predicted whether or not these genes would be secreted in blood and being selected as GBM-biomarkers.

Seven genes were found with a significant effect on the survival of the patients, which were CD81, TMSB10, CST3, C3, CNN3, HSP90AB1, RPL19. Two of these genes were predicted to be secreted in blood (CNN3, C3).

The results of this study show that CNN3, and C3 could be good biomarkers candidates for testing in blood samples, predicting or showing progression of glioblastoma, while the other five genes are candidate biomarkers that can be tested by other methods, without having to get a biopsy directly at the brain.

Keywords:

Biomarker, Cancer, Glioblastoma, GBM

Introduction

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is a malignant tumor that occurs most often in the brain, and develops from star-shaped glial cells, called astrocytes and oligodendrocytes, which support the health of the nerve cells within the brain. It is a severe version of a glioma, which is a certain type of brain cancer. It is often referred to as a grade IV astrocytoma or stage IV glioma. GBM can appear at any age, but in older adults, it appears to occur more frequently, as approximately 50% of people with glioblastoma are older than 65 years old. Initially, signs and symptoms of glioblastoma are nonspecific. Common symptoms include persistent headaches, blurred vision, vomiting, lack of appetite, personality changes, and trouble thinking. It is difficult to cure using normal cancer treatments, but treatments can still somewhat hinder the development of the tumor and decrease signs and symptoms. Normally, an invasive craniotomy is used to diagnose and treat GBM, in which the doctors have to cut open the skull of a patient, and perform highly risky operations (Davis 2016).

A biomarker is an indicator of different biological processes, including pathogenic processes, and ways the body responds to medication. Many biomarkers can be found in blood samples and be detected using simple techniques (Califf 2018).

Because some biomarkers can be found in blood, they can be used to more easily diagnose GBM, and also predict its development. Early diagnosis of GBM can allow for more effective treatment, and the cancer can be treated before it progresses and metastasizes, hindering the cancer's spreading throughout the body (Sasmita et al 2017).

The discovery of biomarkers also contributes to the development of medication because it provides potential genes for the drugs to target. We focus this research work in the identification of candidate biomarkers for GBM using data analysis.

Methods

Data acquisition

First, we collected data from the GDC Database from the National Institute of Health, which provides data for cancer patients, including their gene expression, age at diagnosis, gender, race, survival time, and other clinical data. We filtered through the database to get only the patients with glioblastoma, which was 617 patients, and then used Python scripts to interact with the GDC API to download the information we needed for each patient, which was the gene expression and the number of days they survived after diagnosis.

Two scripts were used: [Data acquisition Script 1](#), [Data acquisition Script 2](#).

Data normalization

We normalized the data by converting the gene expression values to TPM (Transcripts Per Million). We did this by first adding up the gene expression values for all the genes to get a total gene expression value. Then, for each gene, we divided the gene expression value by the total, and then multiplied it by 1 million. This resulted in the TPM for each gene. After this, we sorted each file based on the TPM values. Script used: [Data Normalization Script](#)

Identification of top expressed genes

To identify the most expressed genes across all the patients, we first acquired the top 100 genes from the 161 patients that we had data from. We figured out which genes appeared in the top 100 of any of the patients, which was 675 genes, and then we ordered these genes based on how often they appeared in the top 100 of any of the patients. Script used: [Identification of Top Expressed Genes Script](#)

Pathway analysis

We used DAVID (<https://david.ncifcrf.gov/>) to analyze and annotate, and perform pathway analysis on the 675 genes we found. From DAVID, we found many pathways that included some of the genes from our list. We selected the pathways related to cancer, as they are more related to the topic of our research, and observed which of the genes these cancer pathways contained.

Survival analysis

Then we ran the 675 genes through survival analysis. For each gene in survival analysis, we compared the survival of people who expressed the gene very highly, to people who didn't express the gene as highly. For each gene we calculated the p-value, we only select the genes that had a p-value < 0.05 in the survival analysis.

Scripts used: [Survival Analysis Script 1](#),
[Survival Analysis Script 2](#).

Prediction of secretory signals

We then used the Ensembl REST API (<https://rest.ensembl.org/>) to obtain the amino acid sequences of these genes, and then we used SignalP (<http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/SignalP/>), which is based on a deep learning network to predict secretion, to predict whether or not these proteins are secreted in blood.

Results

Data acquisition

Out of the 617 patients registered with glioblastoma in GDC, only 161 of them had gene expression associated files, so we could only download the data for these patients.

Identification of top expressed genes

We identified the top 100 genes being highly expressed in each patient after data normalization, after combining the list, we found 675 genes. A summary table can be viewed in the Supplementary File 1.

Pathway analysis

The 675 genes were found in KEGG pathways related to cancer and GBM. In addition to these pathways, we found that some of the genes were part of pathways that led to other types of cancer, such as Melanoma, Lung Cancer, Bladder Cancer, and Prostate Cancer.

Survival analysis

We found 7 genes that had a significant effect on the survival of the patients, which were CD81, TMSB10, C3, CST3, CNN3, HSP90AB1, and RPL19. Survival plots are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Survival analysis graphs. The x-axis is the time in days, and the y-axis is the survival probability. The dotted blue line shows the survival of the patients who highly expressed the gene, and the solid yellow line shows the survival of the patients who didn't highly express the gene. The blue area represents the gene is highly expressed in the cohort graphs, while the yellow line is higher in others. When the yellow line is higher, that means that people have lower survival when the gene is highly expressed, and when the blue line is higher, it means that people have higher survival when the gene is highly expressed.

Prediction of secretory signals

In table 1, we show the protein secretion probability for the proteins that are coded for by the 7 genes we got selected from the survival analysis. The SP(Sec/SPI) value here shows the probability that the protein is secreted. CST3 and C3 are the genes that code for a protein that is predicted to be secreted.

ENSG00000034510 (TMSB10)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000233143.4	Not Secreted	0.001145

ENSG00000096384 (HSP90AB1)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000360709.5	Not Secreted	0.000237
ENSP00000325875.3	Not Secreted	0.000237
ENSP00000360609.1	Not Secreted	0.000237
ENSP00000481908.1	Not Secreted	0.000237

ENSG00000101439 (CST3)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000381448.1	Secreted	0.994610
ENSP00000366124.3	Secreted	0.994610
ENSP00000381446.1	Secreted	0.994610

ENSG00000108298 (RPL19)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000225430.4	Not Secreted	0.000727
ENSP00000504751.1	Not Secreted	0.001587
ENSP00000502971.1	Not Secreted	0.000727
ENSP00000504153.1	Not Secreted	0.000727
ENSP00000463985.1	Not Secreted	0.000718
ENSP00000504028.1	Not Secreted	0.000727
ENSP00000464538.1	Not Secreted	0.000479
ENSP00000462938.1	Not Secreted	0.000479
ENSP00000503598.1	Not Secreted	0.000552

ENSG00000110651 (CD81)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000433178.1	Not Secreted	0.221842
ENSP00000432723.1	Not Secreted	0.208221
ENSP00000263645.5	Not Secreted	0.006746
ENSP00000435633.1	Not Secreted	0.001618
ENSP00000437242.1	Not Secreted	0.221842
ENSP00000433767.1	Not Secreted	0.027526
ENSP00000433904.1	Not Secreted	0.028213
ENSP00000432497.1	Not Secreted	0.012975
ENSP00000370424.3	Not Secreted	0.043183
ENSP00000432249.1	Not Secreted	0.016577
ENSP00000431780.1	Not Secreted	0.221842
ENSP00000432033.1	Not Secreted	0.003036

ENSG00000117519 (CNN3)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000359225.4	Not Secreted	0.001192
ENSP00000401452.1	Not Secreted	0.000553
ENSP00000440081.1	Not Secreted	0.000553
ENSP00000377752.4	Not Secreted	0.001192

ENSG00000125730 (C3)		
# ID	Prediction	SP(Sec/SPI)
ENSP00000245907.4	Secreted	0.986691
ENSP00000469482.1	Not Secreted	0.001257
ENSP00000471384.1	Not Secreted	0.177883
ENSP00000469744.1	Not Secreted	0.002153
ENSP00000472044.1	Not Secreted	0.002798

Table 1. Predictive secretion of proteins.

Discussion

Glioblastoma is an important disease because it is a brain cancer that is extremely aggressive and dangerous, however, currently there are no biomarkers used for early diagnosis or prevention of disease progression. Biomarkers are important to GBM because diagnosis without them is much more difficult. Performing a biopsy on the brain results in worse effects compared to biopsies on other parts of the body, as surgeons have to get through the skull to get to the brain, and it is also a high risk for the patient to operate on brain tissue. Because some biomarkers can be found in blood, they can be used to more easily diagnose GBM, and also predict its development.

The analyzes performed allows us to predict 7 genes, CD81, TMSB10, C3, CST3, CNN3, HSP90AB1, and RPL19, that can be used as potential biomarkers for GBM, and C3 and CST3 are predicted to be secreted, increasing its potential to be detected in blood or other body fluids.

The gene Thymosin b10 (TMSB10), a member of the thymosin family, is involved in various physiological processes, including tissue regeneration and inflammatory regulation. Moreover, it has been found to be upregulated in many types of carcinoma. It has been previously reported to be a biomarker of cancer, however they were finding biomarkers for clear cell renal cell carcinoma, rather than glioblastoma (Pan et al 2020).

The gene HSP90AB1 is also associated with cancer as it has been reported that it promoted endothelial cell-dependent tumor angiogenesis in hepatocellular carcinoma, stating that tube formation activities of human endothelial cells significantly increased when HSP90AB 1 was overexpressed (Meng et al 2017)

In the case of Cystatin C (CST3), it is also considered a biomarker in both endometrial cancer and urothelial cancer, and also that around 80% of glioma patients expressed this gene (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/ENSG00000101439-CST3/pathology>)

The ribosomal protein gene RPL19 abrogates the aggressive phenotype of human prostate cancer. RPL19 can help containing malignant tumors, while leaving non-malignant tissues unaffected (Bee et al 2011). This correlates with our research because we found that RPL19 increases the survival of glioblastoma patients.

The CD81 gene was previously reported to be an inducer for breast cancer, meaning that it helps the process of breast cancer take place, as it can sometimes assist in the process of converting epithelial cells to cancer cells. It was also found to increase the growth and metastasis for bone cancer, or osteosarcoma, as the study found that mice with the CD81 injected into them fared much worse and were more affected by the cancer than the positive control group (Uretmen Kagiali et al 2019; Mizoshiri et al 2019)

While we found higher expression of CNN3 to increase the survival rate for patients with glioblastoma, it has been reported that high expression of CNN3 caused poorer survival rates for people with osteosarcoma and silencing the gene caused it to inhibit tumor growth and lung metastasis (Dai et al 2020).

The Complement C3 gene (C3) has been reported that high expression of C3 can activate a pathway that leads to the development and/or progression of gastric cancer (Yuan et al 2020).

Conclusion

Our work presented seven new genes as possible cancer biomarkers for glioblastoma, that could lead to better diagnosis and disease progression measures. However, there are more experimental validations needed to indicate if the presented list of candidates can be used to help patients or included in new therapeutic areas.

Funding

This study was supported by the SkoolMentor program [<https://www.skoolmentor.com/>].

References

1. Davis ME. Glioblastoma: Overview of Disease and Treatment. *Clin J Oncol Nurs*. 2016;20(5 Suppl):S2-S8. doi:10.1188/16.CJON.S1.2-8
2. Califf RM. Biomarker definitions and their applications. *Exp Biol Med (Maywood)*. 2018;243(3):213-221. doi:10.1177/1535370217750088
3. Sasmita AO, Wong YP, Ling APK. Biomarkers and therapeutic advances in glioblastoma multiforme. *Asia Pac J Clin Oncol*. 2018 Feb;14(1):40-51. doi: 10.1111/ajco.12756. Epub 2017 Aug 25. PMID: 28840962.
4. Pan Q, Cheng G, Liu Y, Xu T, Zhang H, Li B. TMSB10 acts as a biomarker and promotes progression of clear cell renal cell carcinoma. *Int J Oncol*. 2020 May;56(5):1101-1114. doi: 10.3892/ijo.2020.4991. Epub 2020 Feb 19. PMID: 32319572; PMCID: PMC7115359.
5. Meng J, Liu Y, Han J, Tan Q, Chen S, Qiao K, Zhou H, Sun T, Yang C. Hsp90 β promoted endothelial cell-dependent tumor angiogenesis in hepatocellular carcinoma. *Mol Cancer*. 2017 Mar 31;16(1):72. doi: 10.1186/s12943-017-0640-9. PMID: 28359326; PMCID: PMC5374580.
6. Bee A, Brewer D, Beesley C, Dodson A, Forootan S, Dickinson T, Gerard P, Lane B, Yao S, Cooper CS, Djamgoz MB, Gosden CM, Ke Y, Foster CS. siRNA knockdown of ribosomal protein gene RPL19 abrogates the aggressive phenotype of human prostate cancer. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(7):e22672. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0022672. Epub 2011 Jul 22. PMID: 21799931; PMCID: PMC3142177.
7. Uretmen Kagiali ZC, Sanal E, Karayel Ö, Polat AN, Saatci Ö, Ersan PG, Trappe K, Renard BY, Önder TT, Tuncbag N, Şahin Ö, Ozlu N. Systems-level Analysis Reveals Multiple Modulators of Epithelial-mesenchymal Transition and Identifies DNAJB4 and CD81 as Novel Metastasis Inducers in Breast Cancer. *Mol Cell Proteomics*. 2019 Sep;18(9):1756-1771. doi: 10.1074/mcp.RA119.001446. Epub 2019 Jun 20. PMID: 31221721; PMCID: PMC6731077.
8. Mizoshiri N, Shirai T, Terauchi R, Tsuchida S, Mori Y, Hayashi D, Kishida T, Arai Y, Mazda O, Nakanishi T, Kubo T. The tetraspanin CD81 mediates the growth and metastases of human osteosarcoma. *Cell Oncol (Dordr)*. 2019 Dec;42(6):861-871. doi: 10.1007/s13402-019-00472-w. Epub 2019 Sep 7. PMID: 31494861.
9. Dai F, Luo F, Zhou R, Zhou Q, Xu J, Zhang Z, Xiao J, Song L. Calponin 3 is associated with poor prognosis and regulates proliferation and metastasis in osteosarcoma. *Aging (Albany NY)*. 2020 Jul 14;12(14):14037-14049. doi: 10.18632/aging.103224. Epub 2020 Jul 14. PMID: 32667904; PMCID: PMC7425500.
10. Yuan K, Ye J, Liu Z, Ren Y, He W, Xu J, He Y, Yuan Y. Complement C3 overexpression activates JAK2/STAT3 pathway and correlates with gastric cancer progression. *J Exp Clin Cancer Res*. 2020 Jan 13;39(1):9. doi: 10.1186/s13046-019-1514-3. PMID: 31928530; PMCID: PMC6956509.